

MODERN TECHNOLOGY OF ARTIFICIAL INSEMINATION IN DOMESTIC ANIMALS

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SUMMARY: By applying the technology of artificial insemination (AI) remarkable progress has been achieved in livestock production over the past 50 years. The basic requirement of modern livestock production is obtaining the maximum number of insemination doses per ejaculate, the possibility of long-term storage of the inseminated doses, as well as achieving the maximum fertility rate of inseminated females. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to present new findings on the modern technology of artificial insemination of domestic animals.

Key words: AI, technology, fertility, domestic animals.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial insemination (AI) is the basic and the most important biotechnological method, which has been used in intensive livestock production for more than 60 years (Foote, 2002). Application of artificial insemination led to great improvements in livestock production due to numerous advantages of artificial insemination compared with natural insemination. The most important advantages of artificial insemination are: producing considerably more offspring from genetically superior males, the possibility of effective prevention of spreading of contagious diseases, the possibility of long-term storage of the sperm from males with genetically desirable traits, easy transport of sperm over long distances, etc (Stančić and Veselinović, 2002). The significance and the scope of AI application is best illustrated by the fact that the world's annual production today is over 300 million insemination doses of bull sperm, around 90 million of sperm doses of boars and around 8 million doses of ram sperm (Thibier and Wagner, 2002).

The technology of AI is constantly evolving with the main aims to: (a) achieve the maximum degree of fertility of inseminated females, (b) maximise the number of insemination doses per ejaculate, (c) ensure the maximum hygiene of AI application, and (d) achieve maximum economic efficiency of AI technology (Ponsart et al., 2004). In this regard, contemporary research has been particularly focused on finding efficient methods for evaluation of sperm quality, methods for efficient dilution and long-term storage of insemination doses of sperm of different animal species, techniques of in-

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seminating females, determining the optimal moment for insemination, efficient methods of estrus detection and synchronisation, etc (Foote, 2002).

BRIEF HISTORY OF ARTIFICIAL INSEMINATION

The first written documents related to artificial insemination date from the seventeenth century, when Leeuwenhoek (1678), using microscope magnification of 270 times, saw movements of spermatozoa, which he called “animalcules”. More than 100 years later, the Italian scientist Lazzaro Spallanzani (1784) artificially inseminated a bitch, which whelped three pups 62 days later. However, it was more than 100 years afterwards that Heape et al. (1897) reported that in different countries artificial insemination of rabbits, dogs and horses was carried out successfully. Practical application of AI in animal husbandry was initiated in Russia by the academician E.I. Ivanov in 1899. Ivanov was the first to develop the methodology of sperm quality control, and formulate diluent composition for sperm and the methods of selecting genetically superior males for the use in AI technology (Ivanov, 1922). His work was continued also in Russia by Milanov (1938), who developed the basic principles of today’s AI technology (taking sperm by artificial vagina, semen dilution, insemination technique, etc), especially in sheep and cattle (Milovanov, 1964). Milovanov’s results were subsequently developed by Japanese scientists (Ishikawa, Ito, Niwa, Sato, Yamane and others), whose results were described in detail by Niwa (1958) and Nishikawa (1964). Sudden development of AI application in cattle began in the USA in early 40s of the twentieth century (Salisbury et al., 1978), while AI in pigs started in Japan (Ito et al., 1948). Significant contribution in development of the basic principles and methods of modern AI technology was made by the scientists from Cambridge University (UK), C. Polge, A.U. Smith and A.S. Parkers (Polge, 1956). AI technology has been developed also in other countries (Denmark, Germany, France, the USA, and others). In our country (former Yugoslavia), AI was significantly developed in the second half of the twentieth century, on large industrial cattle and pig farms, especially in the Federal Republic of Slovenia, the Federal Republic of Croatia, and the Federal Republic of Serbia (Perkućin et al., 1965; Miljković, 1969; Mišković et al., 1987).

Starting from the second half of the twentieth century, artificial insemination has been more and more massively used in livestock production, and today it represents the most important biotechnological method of improving livestock production (Ponsart et al., 2004).

AI IN CATTLE

Artificial insemination of cattle began with fresh sperm doses, diluted with yolk-citrate diluent (Salisbury et al., 1941). However, the technology of long-term storage of insemination doses by deep freezing in liquid nitrogen and at the temperature -196°C was shortly developed. Today over 90% of AI in cows is performed with the doses thawed after storage in deep-frozen state.

Modern technology of AI in cattle involves applying methods of native semen quality control, sperm dilution, long-term storage of insemination doses, insemination techniques, determination of the optimal moment for insemination and estrus synchro-

nization in a larger number of cows intended for simultaneous insemination (DuPont, 2007; Alm-Packalen, 2009; Foote, 2002, Troxel, 2010; Zeron et al., 2010).

Today, a dose for AI in cows is 0.25 ml (i.e. a mini straw), containing 12 to 15 x 10⁶ of progressively motile spermatozoa (Johnson et al., 1995; Parish and Larson, 2010). Insemination is performed intracervically, with a special catheter, and with a dose which was thawed at the temperature 37 to 38°C immediately prior to insemination (Parish and Larson, 2010). For the successful insemination it is very important to determine the optimal time for insemination. Namely, the maximum conception rate is achieved if insemination is performed around 10 to 12 hours before ovulation. Therefore, it is necessary to apply an efficient methodology of estrus detection in cows, which is often a problem on farms since estrus lasts rather short (often less than 12 hours). It is thus the best to detect estrus by observation of external signals of estrus at least 4 times a day at equal time intervals, combined with rectal examination. It is becoming more common to use vasectomised bulls which detect estrous cows most efficiently (Foote, 2002), as well as various models of electronic monitoring of cows' behaviour (Nebel et al., 2000). Today the methods of efficient synchronization of estrus and ovulation are well developed, so a high level of successful conception rate can be achieved also by fixed-time insemination without detection of the estrus signals (Nebel et al., 2000; Grafenau et al., 2008).

The development of sperm-sexing technology (sexing – the separation of sexes) of spermatozoa, and DNA quantification with the method of flow cytometry (Johnson and Seidel, 1999) enable even wider application of AI in the development of livestock production. Namely, by insemination of cows with the doses which contain “male” or “female” spermatozoa, it is possible to obtain calves of a particular sex, as desired by the producer.

AI IN PIGS

In industrial conditions today, more than 80% of sows and gilts are artificially inseminated by classical intracervical insemination (Gadea, 2003). This technology involves the use of insemination doses of fresh diluted semen, which contain 3 to 5 x 10⁹ of progressively motile spermatozoa (Alm et al., 2006; Stančić et al., 2006; Stančić et al., 2010). Doses of liquid diluted sperm are stored at the temperature of +17°C, and they are most commonly used within 1 to 2 days after taking the sperm from boars (Johnson et al., 2000). On the average, around 1,300 insemination doses are obtained annually from one boar (21 doses per ejaculate), which is sufficient for successful insemination of only 300 sows per year (Singleton, 2001). In our country, the number (%) of artificially inseminated breeding sows is considerably lower compared with the developed European countries. However, there is a need for increasing the number of obtained insemination doses on the annual basis, especially of genetically superior boars (Staničić et al., 2007; Stančić et al., 2008; Stančić et al., 2009).

Consequently, there is the growing need for increasing reproductive exploitation of genetically superior boars. Therefore, the possibilities of obtaining a considerably larger number of insemination doses per boar on the annual basis have been researched (Glossop, 2000; Stančić, 2000; Stančić et al., 2006; Stančić et al., 2008). Such increase can be achieved by a more significant reduction of the number of spermatozoa in one insemination dose, from the current 3 to 5 billion, to 1 to 2 billion (Belstra, 2002). The use

of insemination doses with significantly reduced number of spermatozoa, and without significant loss of sow fertility, is enabled by new technology of shallow intrauterine insemination (Vansickle, 2002; Watson et al. 2002; Belstra, 2004; Roseboom et al., 2004; Mezalira et al., 2005; Stančić et al., 2006; Stančić et al., 2007; Radović et al., 2006; Radović et al., 2007; Stančić et al., 2010). For the shallow intrauterine insemination (in the body of the uterus) modified catheters for classical intracervical insemination are used. Namely, a thin, more flexible catheter, through which sperm is deposited in the body of uterus, is inserted through the classical catheter. The insemination procedure is as follows: the top of the classical catheter is inserted through the cervical canal, in the same way as in the classical insemination. Then, the thinner catheter is slowly inserted all the way to the body of the uterus (around 20 cm in length), where the deposition of the sperm dose is made (Grafenau et al. 2004).

Further reduction of the volume and number of spermatozoa per an insemination dose can be achieved by using deep intrauterine insemination. This insemination is performed by transcervical insertion of a special catheter deep into the uterine horn. The aim is to deposit the insemination doses as close as possible to the top of the uterine horn, i.e. uterotubal junction (Rath, 2002; Grafenau et al., 2004). The results so far have shown that it is sufficient to insert a flexible catheter of 30 to 40 cm into the horn, cranially from the bifurcation of the uterus, in order to achieve good results of fertility in sows inseminated with the doses of 10 to 20 ml, containing 1 to 5 x 10⁸ spermatozoa (Wolken et al., 2002; Roca et al., 2003; Wongtawan et al., 2005; Vasquez et al., 2005). The satisfactory conception rate is achieved also by the doses of 0.5 ml with 1 x 10⁶ of progressively motile sperm, if such a dose is directly deposited into the top of the uterine horn surgically (laparotomy or laparoscopy) (Krüger et al., 2000; Wolken, 2001).

Apart from the quality of the insemination dose and technique of the conducted insemination, in order to achieve a high degree of fertility of inseminated sows, it is necessary that insemination should be at the optimal time in relation to the beginning of the standing reflex, i.e. the moment of ovulation. In this regard, the application of efficient estrus detection technology is very important (Spronk et al., 1997; Kaeoket et al., 2005; Radović et al., 2006; Stančić et al., 2007; Stančić et al., 2007; Stančić et al., 2008; Stančić et al., 2009; Stančić et al., 2010).

AI IN SHEEP AND GOATS

Artificial insemination of sheep and goats is applied in industrial production in order to get a considerably higher number of lambs and genetically superior rams, and to increase the efficiency of reproductive exploitation of rams (Donovan et al., 2001; Sohnrey and Holtz, 2005). The technique used is vaginal, cervical, transcervical and intrauterine (via laparoscopy) deposition of insemination doses. The doses of fresh diluted sperm or deep frozen doses are used (Donovan et al., 2001; Leethongdee, 2009). The conception rate is much lower in sheep inseminated with the doses which were deep frozen, both when insemination was carried out in a spontaneous and synchronised estrus (Donovan et al., 2004; Dogan et al., 2004). Recently, the technique of laparoscopic intrauterine insemination has been applied with the doses of 0.25 ml, which contain 80 x 10⁶ spermatozoa. With this technique, 60 to 70 % of successful conception is achieved (Luther, 2008), which is similar to the conception achieved with the classical cervical

insemination with the doses of fresh diluted semen, containing 200×10^6 spermatozoa in the dose of 0.25 ml (Leethongdee, 2009).

AI IN HORSES

For artificial insemination of mares, the most commonly used doses are liquid diluted sperm of 10 to 15 ml, containing 500 to 600×10^6 of progressively motile spermatozoa. Native ejaculates should have at least 60 % of progressive motility (Heckenbichler et al., 2010). These doses can be stored at $+20^\circ\text{C}$ or $+5^\circ\text{C}$, not longer than 24 to 48 hours. After this time, the achieved conception rate of inseminated mares decreases significantly by 7 to 10% with the insemination doses kept at $+20^\circ\text{C}$, and about 40% with the insemination doses kept at $+5^\circ\text{C}$ (Newkombe et al., 2005).

In recent years, artificial insemination of mares with the doses having had long-term deep-freeze storage has been used more frequently. The results so far have shown that the number of progressively motile spermatozoa in these doses ranges from 100 to 600×10^6 , while it is considered that the optimal number of spermatozoa in the dose is around 250×10^6 . The achieved conception rate significantly varies from 50 to 90%, depending on the applied technology of deep freezing, the content of sperm diluent, duration of storing of insemination doses, technology of the doses thawing, insemination technology (place of sperm deposition in female sexual organs and the optimal time of insemination of mares), the quality of sperm of certain stallions, as well as the season (mating season or anestrus season) in which the native ejaculates were obtained (Metcalf, 2007; Barbacini and Loomis, 2007).

Significant reduction of the volume of insemination doses and the number of progressively motile sperm in doses can be achieved by deep intrauterine insemination of mares. With this technology, using endoscopy, a special catheter is transcervically inserted close to uterotubal junction of a mare's uterine horn. In this way, after visualisation of the papilla of caudal isthmus of oviduct, the dose of 5 ml of sperm, containing 50 to 100×10^6 of progressively motile spermatozoa, is deposited in the surroundings of the papilla (Pycock, 2005).

AI IN DOGS

Intravaginal insemination with doses of fresh diluted sperm is an efficient classical method of artificial insemination of bitches, and this method gives good results of fertility (Rota et al., 1999). However, the use of insemination doses which had a long-term deep-freeze storage gives highly variable results, depending on the sperm quality, the deposition site of insemination doses (intravaginal or intrauterine), type of insemination catheter, as well as the breed of the inseminated bitches. Thus, Linde-Forsberg et al. (1999) found that the successful conception rate is 84% after intrauterine and 59% after intravaginal insemination with the doses kept deep frozen. Intrauterine insemination doses of fresh diluted sperm give considerably better conception rate (86.7%) compared with the insemination doses kept deep frozen (60.7%). Litter size is also higher (6 pups) after insemination with fresh sperm, compared with the insemination with deep frozen sperm (4 pups) (Nižanski, 2006).

In the modern technology of artificial insemination of bitches with the doses stored deep frozen, the doses of 2 to 2.5 ml, containing 2×10^8 of progressively motile sperm, are used. To dilute the sperm, tris-fructose-citrate diluent with 8% (v/v) glycerol and 20% (v/v) egg yolk is used. Thawing of the frozen doses is performed at 37°C for 30 seconds. Intrauterine insemination is applied exclusively and it is performed transcervically or with the method of laparoscopy. By using this method 62 to 91% of successful conception is achieved (Thomassen et al., 2006).

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SAVREMENA TEHNOLOGIJA VEŠTAČKOG OSEMENJAVANJA DOMAĆIH ŽIVOTINJA

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Izvod

Primenom tehnologije veštačkog osemenjavanja (VO) je postignut ogrman napredak u stočarskoj proizvodnji, tokom poslednjih 50 godina. Osnovni zahtev savremene stočarske proizvodnje je dobijanje maksimalnog broja inseminacionih doza po ejakulatu, mogućnost dugotrajnog čuvanja inseminacionih doza, kao i postizanje maksimalne vrednosti fertiliteta osemenjenih ženki. Zbog toga je cilj ovog rada da se prikažu novija saznanja u vezi sa savremenom tehnologijom veštačkog osemenavanja domaćih životinja.

Ključne reči: VO, tehnologija, fertilitet, domaće životinje.

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